

DRINKING WATER QUALITY IN THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA BETWEEN CHALLENGES AND PUBLIC HEALTH PROTECTION

Calitatea apei potabile în Republica Moldova, între provocări și protecția sănătății publice

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Summary. Drinking water quality is a crucial determinant of public health, and the Republic of Moldova faces major challenges in ensuring safe water access. Analysis of official data and international reports reveals significant differences between centralised and decentralised sources: while in urban areas the rate of chemical non-compliance is around 8-10%, in rural areas more than 70% of samples exceed the admissible values. The main problematic indicators are nitrates, fluoride, water hardness, sodium, ammonium and iron, alongside microbiological contamination of wells. Excessive nitrate concentrations are associated with infant methemoglobinemia and oncological risks, whereas elevated fluoride levels cause dental and skeletal fluorosis. Although Law No. 182/2019 aligns the Republic of Moldova with European and WHO standards, the implementation of water safety plans and investment in rural infrastructure remain insufficient. Reducing territorial inequalities and adapting to climate change are key conditions for achieving water security in the country.

Key words: drinking water, water quality, public health, legislation, nitrates, hardness.

Introduction. Drinking water quality represents a fundamental pillar for public health and societal well-being. Access to safe water is recognised as an essential human right and forms the basis of a healthy and productive life¹. The lack of clean drinking water is

¹ World Health Organization: Drinking-water, 2023. [online] <https://www.who.int/news-room/>

directly associated with an increased incidence of infectious diseases, chronic health problems, and major social inequalities. In the Republic of Moldova, the issue of water quality is compounded by the limited availability of resources, making the country one of the most vulnerable in Eastern Europe from the perspective of water security².

The challenges are manifold: limited freshwater resources, outdated supply infrastructure, diffuse pollution originating from agriculture, and persistent local contamination. According to United Nations data on Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 6, in 2022 only about 75% of the population of the Republic of Moldova had access to safely managed drinking water services³. The situation is even more critical in rural areas, where access to quality water remains limited and the population largely depends on unprotected wells or untreated natural springs. A study conducted between 2015 and 2019 revealed an alarming proportion of chemical and microbiological non-compliance. In urban settings, approximately 8.6% of samples from public supply networks were chemically non-compliant, while in rural areas groundwater-based supplies showed about 52% non-compliance. For decentralised sources, the situation was even more concerning, with 77.2% of samples exceeding chemical limits and 47.6% failing microbiological standards⁴. Recent data confirm this negative trend: in 2025, the National Agency for Public Health reported that over 75% of decentralised sources contained contaminated water, and in districts such as Rezina, Călărași, Căușeni, Ștefan Vodă, and Basarabeasca, the proportion exceeded 90%⁵.

Beyond quality issues, the problem of access is aggravated by the insufficiency of resources: the annual availability of water per capita is estimated at around 500 m³, twice lower than the international minimum threshold of 1,000 m³ established to avoid water stress⁶. This situation increases the population's vulnerability to climate change, drought, and soil degradation, factors that limit the natural recharge of groundwater. From a chemical perspective, field investigations have revealed elevated nitrate concentrations, frequently exceeding the maximum admissible limit of 50 mg/L, particularly in areas of intensive agriculture. In addition, in the southern part of the country, fluoride concentrations often exceed recommended levels, ranging from 2 to 14 mg/L, and are associated with cases of dental and skeletal fluorosis. Likewise, high levels of sodium (200-560 mg/L), ammonium (2-10 mg/L), and iron (0.3-2.5 mg/L) have been reported in numerous samples, reducing the organoleptic acceptability of water and indicating persistent contamination of sources⁷.

In addition, surface waters and hand-dug wells in the central region show consistent microbial contamination, which increases the risk of diarrhoeal diseases. These data reflect a profound structural problem that goes beyond the technical dimension of water supply

fact-sheets/detail/drinking-water (accessed 30.08.2025).

² UNECE: Environmental Performance Reviews, 2021. [online] <https://unece.org/environment-policy/environmental-performance-reviews> (accessed 30.08.2025).

³ UNICEF & WHO: Progress on household drinking water, sanitation and hygiene 2000–2024: special focus on inequalities, 2023. [online] <https://washdata.org/> (accessed 28.08.2025).

⁴ National Agency for Public Health, 2020. [online] <https://ansp.md/> (accessed 29.08.2025).

⁵ National Agency for Public Health: Report, 2025. [online] <https://ansp.md/rapoarte> (accessed 29.08.2025).

⁶ UNECE: The Water Convention and the Protocol on Water and Health, 2021. [online] <https://unece.org/environment-policy/environmental-performance-reviews> (accessed 26.08.2025).

⁷ World Health Organization: Sodium in Drinking-water, 2022. [online] <https://www.who.int/docs/default-source/wash-documents/wash-chemicals/sodium-background-document.pdf> (accessed 30.08.2025)

and falls within the broader sphere of public health policies, social equity, and adaptation to climate change. The integration of the provisions of Law No. 182/2019 on drinking water quality into national health and environmental strategies is essential for protecting the population and reducing inequalities in access.

Materials and Methods

To assess the situation and the chemical and microbiological composition of drinking water in the Republic of Moldova, official data and public reports produced by institutions responsible for water quality monitoring were used. The main sources of information included reports of the National Agency for Public Health (ANSP, 2020; 2025), statistical data published by the National Bureau of Statistics, as well as international documents prepared by the World Health Organization, the WHO–UNICEF Joint Monitoring Programme for Water Supply, Sanitation and Hygiene, and the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe.

The analysis focused on comparing empirical data collected at the national level with the maximum admissible limits established by Law No. 182/2019 on drinking water quality, as well as with the reference values from Directive (EU) 2020/2184 and the WHO Guidelines for Drinking-water Quality.

The evaluated indicators included chemical parameters (nitrates, fluoride, total hardness, sodium, ammonium, iron) and microbiological parameters, where data were available.

In the absence of a unified national database, the methodology was based on narrative synthesis. This approach enabled the integration and comparison of results drawn from various official reports and monitoring studies, with the aim of highlighting the main non-compliances and their implications for public health.

Results and Discussion

The comparative analysis of drinking water quality in the Republic of Moldova confirms major discrepancies between centralised and decentralised sources. While urban centralised supply networks show a chemical non-compliance rate of approximately 8-10% of samples, decentralised sources, used mainly in rural areas, record exceedances of chemical and microbiological parameters in more than 70% of cases. This gap highlights not only infrastructural weaknesses but also the lack of effective monitoring and control mechanisms for private wells and small-scale supplies, which remain the primary sources of drinking water for the rural population. This structural disparity highlights the fragility of rural infrastructure and the lack of rigorous control over private wells and springs, which remain the main sources of supply for more than 80% of households. The situation reflects not only a technical issue but also one of social equity, as the rural population is disproportionately exposed to health risks.

Excess nitrate concentrations represent the most widespread form of contamination. The measured values frequently exceed the maximum admissible limit of 50 mg/L, established by Law No. 182/2019 and harmonised with the WHO Guidelines and Directive (EU) 2020/2184. Agricultural sources, through the excessive use of nitrogen-based fertilisers, represent the main factor in groundwater pollution. Prolonged exposure to nitrates is associated with infant methemoglobinaemia (“blue baby syndrome”), but the international literature also confirms additional risks such as gastric cancer, thyroid dysfunction, and endocrine disorders⁸.

Another critical factor is the high concentration of fluoride in the southern part of the country, where values reach up to 14 mg/L, far exceeding the national legal limit of 1.5

⁸ Ward MH, Jones RR, Brender JD, De Kok TM, Weyer PJ, Nolan BT, Villanueva CM, Van Breda SG. Drinking Water Nitrate and Human Health: An Updated Review. In: International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health. 2018; 15(7):1557. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15071557>

mg/L. Although fluoride plays a beneficial role in preventing dental caries, chronic exposure to elevated levels causes dental fluorosis and, in the long term, skeletal fluorosis⁹. Field studies have already documented the presence of these pathologies in affected communities, underscoring the urgency of technical solutions such as the use of alternative sources or the implementation of defluoridation systems. In addition, other relevant parameters such as total hardness, sodium, ammonium, and iron show a heterogeneous distribution across the country. Water hardness, regulated under Law No. 182/2019 at 5°dH, frequently exceeds the recommendations of WHO and the EU. Although it does not constitute a major direct health risk, excessive hardness reduces the acceptability of water, contributes to the formation of kidney stones, and generates deposits within distribution networks. In parallel, high concentrations of sodium (200-560 mg/L) and iron (0.3-2.5 mg/L) alter the organoleptic properties of water, while the presence of ammonium (2-10 mg/L) indicates recent pollution of the sources.

Law No. 182/2019 introduces a major innovation through the requirement to develop “drinking water safety plans.” These, in line with WHO recommendations and Directive (EU) 2020/2184, provide for the assessment and management of risks from source to consumer. The implementation of these plans remains limited, particularly in rural areas where infrastructure is fragmented, financial resources are insufficient, and institutional capacity is weak.

The data analysis also confirms a socio-economic dimension to the problem: the rural population, dependent on wells and springs, is the most exposed to contamination. This raises issues of equity and the fundamental right to health. Territorial inequalities become even more pronounced in the context of climate change and drought, which reduce groundwater recharge and increase the risk of pollutant concentration. Under these conditions, the rigorous enforcement of legal provisions, coupled with investment in modern infrastructure and community education on the use of safe water sources, is essential for strengthening water security and protecting public health.

Conclusions. The analysis of drinking water quality in the Republic of Moldova, in the context of the implementation of Law No. 182/2019, reveals a modernised regulatory framework aligned with European and international standards. Nevertheless, empirical data demonstrate the persistence of non-compliance, particularly in rural areas. The most problematic parameters are nitrates, fluoride, and water hardness, which frequently exceed admissible limits. The implications for public health are significant: infant methemoglobinemia, dental and skeletal fluorosis, risks of kidney stone formation, cardiovascular diseases, as well as increased vulnerability to diarrhoeal diseases due to microbiological contamination. Law No. 182/2019 establishes the premises for a preventive, transparent, and sustainable approach, but its success depends on rigorous implementation and on investment in infrastructure and institutional capacity.

⁹ World Health Organization: Guidelines for drinking-water quality: fourth edition incorporating first addendum. 2017. [online] <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/254637> (accessed 30.08.2025).